

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D2.9 – User Centric Design II

WP2 Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User
Scenarios in iHelp

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Table of Contents

- Executive summary 7
- 1 Introduction and Objectives 8
 - 1.1 Scope 8
 - 1.2 Aim and Objectives..... 8
 - 1.3 Approach 9
 - 1.4 Contents of This Deliverable 9
- 2 Interaction With Other Tasks and Work Packages 10
 - 2.1 Relationship With Other Tasks Within WP2..... 10
 - 2.1.1 User-Relevant Requirements from T2.1..... 10
 - 2.1.2 Sequence of User-Facing System Actions and Activity Diagrams in T2.2..... 11
 - 2.2 Relationship With WP5 and WP6..... 11
 - 2.3 Relationship with WP7 12
- 3 User-Driven Design Process and Results Reported in D2.8 13
 - 3.1 Process Requirements for Medical Devices 13
 - 3.2 Process Implemented in iHelp..... 13
 - 3.3 Summary Contents of D2.8 14
 - 3.3.1 User-Facing Use Case Models 14
 - 3.3.2 Model Builder’s Interface 15
 - 3.3.3 Health Professional’s Interface 16
 - 3.3.4 Individual’s Interface 17
 - 3.3.5 Policy Maker’s Interface 17
 - 3.4 Feedback on Key Screen Designs Oct 2021..... 19
- 4 User Feedback Obtained on Updated Wireframes 20
 - 4.1 Clinicians Facing Wireframes Workshop..... 20
 - 4.2 User Facing Wireframes Workshop..... 21
 - 4.2.1 Healthentia Application Demonstration 21
 - 4.2.2 Suggestions and Concerns..... 21
 - 4.3 Policy and Model Builders Wireframes Workshop 22
 - 4.3.1 Demonstration of Creating a Dashboard 22
 - 4.3.2 Social Media Analysis Interface 22
 - 4.4 Conclusion 22
- 5 Final user interface blueprints for generic iHelp system..... 24
 - 5.1 Model Builder’s Interface..... 24
 - 5.2 Health Professional’s Interface 27
 - 5.2.1 Risk Assessment Group of Use Cases 28

- 5.2.2 Risk Mitigation Use Case 31
- 5.2.3 Advice Review Use Case 36
- 5.2.4 Advice Follow-Up Use Case 36
- 5.3 Individual’s Interface 39
- 5.4 Policy Maker’s Interface 42
 - 5.4.1 Login Screen 42
 - 5.4.2 Applications List..... 42
 - 5.4.3 Application Details..... 43
 - 5.4.4 Create Application 44
 - 5.4.5 Alerts Information 45
 - 5.4.6 Follow Users 47
- 6 User Interface Design Guidelines 48
 - 6.1 General Principles of UI Design 48
 - 6.1.1 Learnability 48
 - 6.1.2 Flexibility..... 49
 - 6.1.3 Robustness 49
 - 6.2 Desktop Interface 50
 - 6.3 Mobile Interfaces 51
- 7 Usability Evaluation KPIs..... 55
 - 7.1 General Evaluation Principles..... 55
 - 7.2 Formative evaluation by usability experts 55
 - 7.3 User-based usability testing – Summative evaluation 55
- 8 Summary and Conclusion 57
 - 8.1 Summary of the Deliverable..... 57
 - 8.2 Further work..... 57
- Bibliography..... 58
- List of Acronyms 59
- Annex A - Recommended Colour Chart 60

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Flowchart for the activities in D2.8 and D2.9.....	14
Figure 2: Use case model of overall iHelp interaction with its Users.....	15
Figure 3: Social Media Analyser use case model – the perspective of Policy Maker user type.....	18
Figure 4: Model Builder UI menu.....	24
Figure 5: Model Builder UI.....	25
Figure 6: Custom dashboard example.....	26
Figure 7: Model Explainability Interface.....	27
Figure 8: Login screen for the health professional - Password-protected access ensures confidentiality of data.....	27
Figure 9: Health professional's dashboard.....	28
Figure 10: Initial Screen detail of Risk Assessment Use Case.....	28
Figure 11: The system prompts for missing HHR data and additional information.....	28
Figure 12: Displaying the calculated lifetime risk of developing pancreatic cancer.....	29
Figure 13: The clinician disagrees with the conclusion.....	30
Figure 14: Conclusion of the initial risk assessment group of use cases when the elevated predicted risk is confirmed by the health professional.....	31
Figure 15: Retrieving patient details during the risk mitigation meeting.....	32
Figure 16: The screens for “test results retrieved” and “factors impacting risk”.....	33
Figure 17: The AI model in iHelp produces a shortlist of measures which can help reduce the risk for this specific patient.....	34
Figure 18: Detailed planning of risk reduction.....	35
Figure 19: An example of a risk mitigation plan focused on reducing weight and alcohol consumption.....	36
Figure 20. Interface for Reviewing AI-generated messages from the system to the patient.....	37
Figure 21. The “advice follow-up” screen.....	37
Figure 22: Redress shortfall within the Advice Follow-up use case.....	38
Figure 23: Screen numbers 1 and 2 of the Virtual Coaching UI wireframe.....	39
Figure 24: Screen numbers 3 and 4 of the Virtual Coaching UI wireframe.....	40
Figure 25: A mock-up screen showing a longer part of a conversation (left) and an actual conversation with the implemented Virtual Coach in the Healthentia app (right).....	41
Figure 26: The Login screen for the Social Media Analyser Tool.....	42
Figure 27: Wireframe showing the list of existing applications within the Social Media Analyser Tool.....	43
Figure 28: Wireframe showing the details of a specific application within the Social Media Analyser Tool.....	44
Figure 29: Wireframe showing the Create Application screen.....	45

Figure 30: Wireframe showing the screen where detailed conditions and rules of each application can be defined. 46

Figure 31: Wireframe showing the main alerts screen where alerts of all active applications are shown. 47

Figure 32: Example layout and colours for the health professional desktop interface – a main panel version. 50

Figure 33: Example layout and colours for the health professional desktop interface - multiple panels version. 51

Figure 34: Proposed landing page on mobile interface (left) and processing (thinking) page (right). . 52

Figure 35: Example colour scheme for the mobile interface - Progress to Goals screen (left) and Daily Status screen (right). 53

Figure 36: The iHelp theme as implemented within the Healthentia application. 54

Executive summary

This deliverable is the second output of T2.4 – “User Centred Design”, targeting to provide a user centred design process and design thinking methodology that guides the design and development of the iHelp platform, as also to align the iHelp architecture and components with user centred design principles. Indeed, the software produced by iHelp will only be effective if users and patients continue to use the system for long enough to have an impact on their long-term behaviour and hence on their long-term risk of developing pancreatic cancer.

The nature of the user centred design process motivates a major difference between the outputs of T2.4 – “User Centred Design” compared to the other tasks in WP2 – “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp”. Moreover, it is worth to mention that D2.8 – “User Centric Design I” and D2.9 – “User Centric Design II” are separate deliverables covering results from different parts of the user centred design process and complementing each other in a whole, whilst the deliverables of the other tasks, for example D2.6 – “Functional and Non-Functional Specifications I” and D2.7 – “Functional and Non-Functional Specifications II” are two versions of the same deliverable, covering more detailed specifications as their task progresses. Thus, whilst an observer at the end of the project can read only D2.7 and skip D2.6, they will need to read both D2.8 and D2.9 to understand the results of T2.4.

The areas of focus of the current deliverable are:

- **User involvement in formulating system functionality and interfaces** is one of the main requirements of the regulations governing the development of medical-related software like iHelp. To ensure this user involvement, we conducted a series of workshops, where our pilot users were able to reflect on the proposed software functionality and to feed back their wishes in terms of improvement of this functionality. The results of the first round of workshops were reported in the preceding deliverable, i.e., D2.8 – “User Centric Design I” (M., N., C., + 21), whilst the results of the second round are reported in this deliverable (D2.9 – “User Centric Design II”).
- The **finalised versions of the wireframes** illustrating the agreed functionality of iHelp as seen by its users are presented here. These are based on the functional requirements produced by T2.1 – “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp” and represent the results of several iterations of user-driven development, including two workshops with our pilots, and earlier iterations with project partners and pilots.
- The **Usability Engineering Guidelines** are one of the main outputs of this deliverable, and they have been derived after carefully considering the characteristics of the different types of users, and the circumstances in which they will use the system, such as brightness, noise, etc.
- The **Usability Evaluation Criteria** described in this deliverable are the major contribution to the evaluation of the user interfaces that will be done later on in iHelp. These Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are developed after working closely with end-users to ensure the long-term use of the iHelp software.

1 Introduction and Objectives

1.1 Scope

This deliverable is the second official output of T2.4 – “User Centred Design”, describing the second stage of the user centred design process and so complementing rather than superseding the previous deliverable D2.8 – “User Centric Design I”. It describes the finalised user interface designs of the iHelp, developed taking into account the feedback by its end users, aiming to deliver interfaces which are easy to understand and are also perceived as enjoyable for the end users.

In this second stage of T2.4 – “User Centred Design” we prepared updated versions of the wireframes illustrating iHelp functionality from the perspective of four different groups of users, i.e., clinicians, patients/individuals¹, model builders, and decision-makers. We evaluated this second version through a set of user feedback workshops that took place on the 10th, 11th, and 14th of March 2022, and here we report on this feedback and how it impacts the wireframes. We also provide general principles for the user interface design to make it user-friendly. The KPIs for usability evaluation are also described to incorporate user interface design guidelines.

1.2 Aim and Objectives

This deliverable reflects the second phase of T2.4 – “User Centred Design”, which is focused on the aim of ensuring that the iHelp software design is based on end-user requirements, needs and specific characteristics of our target types of users. It must be in line with the needs of different types of users to encourage continuous use and achieve long-term health benefits.

The objectives to achieve this aim are as follows:

- Identification of major types of system users using the technique of personas so that the attributes of that particular set of users are described in the system.
- Identifying and presenting the main user-facing use case models and interactions.
- Low-fidelity wireframes are developed to ensure a user-focused design at this initial stage of iHelp development.
- User feedback workshops, powered by the wireframes will test the level of satisfaction of the pilots on the developed wireframes and provide feedback for improvements.
- User interface design guidelines to be provided for the user-facing iHelp modules.
- A set of evaluation KPIs will be provided to software developers on iHelp, and the software will be evaluated against these KPIs later on in the project.

Of these objectives, this deliverable (i.e., D2.9 – “User Centric Design II”) focuses on Objectives 3-6 of WP2 as introduced in the DoA. While Objectives 1 and 2 were accomplished in the previous deliverable, i.e., D2.8 – “User Centric Design I”.

¹ By “patients” or “individuals” we also mean people who are simply interested in checking their chances of developing pancreatic cancer and reducing these chances. Using the more generic “users” for this group would be confusing with the other users of the iHelp system such as clinicians, model builders, etc.

1.3 Approach

The wireframes developed for the iHelp software are based on user-centric and task-based design principles. First, key user groups are identified and then their expectations from the software are considered, as captured by the deliverables of T2.1 – “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp”. The major interaction components of the system are mapped to the user interface and the corresponding use cases. The low-fidelity wireframes are presented to the pilots to measure the usability of the system for the end-users before implementing the actual interfaces for the iHelp software.

Using the accumulated user feedback, theoretical input featured in D2.8 – “User Centric Design I”, and the understanding of context, we proceed to derive user interface design guidelines and the KPIs which we will use within WP7 – “Impact Assessment” to evaluate the iHelp interface produced by software development partners on the project.

1.4 Contents of This Deliverable

Section 2 describes the interaction of T2.4 – “User Centred Design” with the other tasks within WP2 – “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp” and its relation to WP5 – “AI for Early Risk Assessment and Personalised Recommendations”, WP6 – “Clinical Validation and Pilot Studies” and WP7 – “Impact Assessment”. The user-driven design process and the other results reported in D2.8 – “User Centric Design” are summarised in Section 3, providing a starting context of this deliverable. The workshops organized to obtain feedback from the pilots are detailed in Section 4, which shows the discussion and suggestions that were useful to make the iHelp system beneficial and ensure long-term use for the end-users. Final user interface blueprints for the generic iHelp system produced after the workshops are presented in Section 5. Section 6 describes the design guidelines for the user interface that will help developers make interfaces according to the user requirements and templates for mobile and desktop interfaces are shown to reflect these guidelines. The finalised iHelp user interfaces will be evaluated based on the evaluation process, criteria and KPIs explained in Section 7. Finally, a summary of this deliverable is presented in Section 8.

2 Interaction With Other Tasks and Work Packages

The main focus of T2.4 – “User Centred Design” is to provide design guidelines to the technology developers so that the technical components of the iHelp software are aligned with target users' expectations.

The main sources of input for these guidelines and the key requirements and use cases are taken from T2.1 – “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp”. The components that will be user-facing are identified from T2.2 – “Reference Architecture Specifications”, and the flows of interactions between the users and the system are aligned with the specifications produced by T2.3 – “Functional and Non-Functional Specifications”. What is more, T2.4 – “User Centred Design” also provides guidance for the user interfaces for personalised advice and monitoring to make it effective and enjoyable.

The output of the WP2 – “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp” tasks serves as a specification and guidance for the development tasks in WP5 – “AI for Early Risk Assessment and Personalized Recommendations” adapted to the needs of individual pilots in WP6 – “iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies”. These include UI design guidelines, use case activity diagrams and wireframes. The evaluation criteria described in this deliverable will be used to evaluate the iHelp software which will be conducted in the WP7 – “Impact Assessment”. Section 2.1 shows the relationship of T2.4 – “User Centred Design” within WP2 – “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp” and section 2.2 describes the interaction of T2.4 – “User Centred Design” with WP5 – “AI for Early Risk Assessment and Personalized Recommendations” and WP6 – “iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies”. Finally, interaction with WP7 – “Impact Assessment” is shown in section 2.3.

2.1 Relationship With Other Tasks Within WP2

The activities carried out in T2.4 – “User Centred Design” are used to complement other WP2 tasks, i.e., specifying requirements and user scenarios (T2.1) and translating user needs regarding technical and non-technical specifications (T2.3).

2.1.1 User-Relevant Requirements from T2.1

The iHelp project involves different categories of users, T2.1 – “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp” works on finding user requirements from each group reported in D2.1 – “State of the art and requirements analysis I” (M., M., K., + 21). The state-of-the-art technologies are explored to identify future trends, use cases and technical requirements. The SotA will be investigated for the entire project duration to make sure that innovations and objectives are in line with each other. The functionalities of the iHelp system and its mapping to the user requirements are elaborated in D2.1 – “State of the art and requirements analysis I”.

This deliverable is based on the user-driven design process providing guidelines for the technology developers for UI design to make iHelp system more accessible and enjoyable for the end users. Enhancing the function of iHelp based on the user needs and requirements to make it usable for the intended purpose. Some of the functionalities that must be considered for the user-centric design process are as follows:

- Secondary data must be gathered from different types of interfaces i.e., mobile and wearable devices about different health-related conditions. For example, diet intake, physical activity, sleep pattern, body signals, medication, patient enrolment, and user experience (as explained in Section 4.3 of D2.1).

- Clinical Decision Support Suite with Visual Analytic Tools (Section 4.7 of D2.1) provides users with different interfaces for data queries, building dashboards and visualisation of data.
- Delivery Mechanisms for Personalised Healthcare and Real-time Feedback (Section 4.11 of D2.1). The Mobile application “Healthentia” development in the iHelp software is based on the users’ feedback on the identified risk factors, setting goals for relevant risk factors showing achievement and failure to achieve the goals. Conversational coaching and tracking user interaction are also part of this functionality.
- Social Analytics for the Study of Societal Factors and Policy Making (Section 4.12 of D2.1) provides a visual interface for users to analyse discussions on different topics from social media platforms, e.g., Facebook, Twitter and Reddit. It allows to monitor and alert the users on the propagation and emergence of various topics of discussion.

2.1.2 Sequence of User-Facing System Actions and Activity Diagrams in T2.2

WP2 deliverables reflect two different perspectives on the behavioural model of the iHelp system that come from:

- T2.2 – “Reference Architecture Specifications” and T2.3 – “Functional and Non-Functional Specifications”, which use activity diagrams for describing the sequence of actions between system components and external users in each use case; and
- T2.4 – “User Centred Design”, which is focused on the interaction between different categories of users and the system for the different user-facing use case models.

These two perspectives are aligned to fit the desired functionality of the system, and part of this alignment process was reported in D2.8 – “User Centric Design I”.

2.2 Relationship With WP5 and WP6

User interface guidelines are important for the activities that are part of WP5 specifically in the context of these tasks:

- T5.2 – “Design of Personalised Prevention and Intervention Measures”

This task will produce an AI-based decision-support technique which will design personalised advice based on the risk model and the user profile. T2.4 – “User Centred Design” interacts with this task along the second dimension: that of the user profiling and personalised recommendation, where T2.4 – “User Centred Design”. provides main categories of target users/patients exemplified as personas captured in D2.8 – “User Centric Design I”, including background information about these categories of users/patients.

- T5.3 – “Delivery Mechanisms for Personalised Healthcare and Real-Time Feedback”

A mobile application based on the “Healthentia” platform supported by Innovation Sprint will be developed in this task for real-time monitoring and providing decision support functionalities to the users in our pilots. The mobile application needs to engage users in an enjoyable way to ensure it is aligned with user requirements. User interface guidelines described in Section 6 will be applied to ensure effective monitoring.

- T5.4 – “Social Analytics for the Study of Societal Factors and Policy Making”

A social media analysis tool is developed in this task for the policymakers to monitor the discussion of specific topics. The data gathered from social media is used to provide insight information about the societal trends concerning specific policies and public perception of that certain policy. The interface developed for the social media analysis must be easy to understand for non-technical end users so that the data gathered can be used to design new policies and evaluate the exciting ones.

- T5.5 – “Monitoring, Alerting, Feedback and Evaluation Mechanisms”

T5.5 delivers software which allows clinicians to define rules which monitor the progress of the patient against pre-defined goals and alert the clinician and the system if the user is persistently not meeting the goals so that a review of the programme can be undertaken. The user interface design guidelines and evaluation KPIs produced by T2.4 – “User Centred Design” and reported in this deliverable are relevant to the interfaces developed by T5.5.

- WP6 – “iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies”

Another axis of interaction is with the individual pilots within WP6 – “iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies”, where the generic iHelp interfaces designed by T2.4 – “User Centred Design” and reported here will be customised to the needs of the individual pilots. This will make concrete even rather abstract models reported here such as the mobile dialogue manager.

2.3 Relationship with WP7

The impact assessment that will be carried out in WP7 – “Impact Assessment” will use the user centred design approach and evaluate the suitability of the user interfaces developed in iHelp for the target type of users, in a manner described later on in this deliverable. Usability KPIs and metrics defined in Section 7 will be used to evaluate the usability of the iHelp platform in almost all tasks of WP7 specifically in task T7.2: Usability Evaluation of the iHelp Solution.

3 User-Driven Design Process and Results Reported in D2.8

3.1 Process Requirements for Medical Devices

The iHelp software is classified as a Medical Device Class IIa based on the Official Journal of the European Union L117/143, Section 6.3, Rule 111². The design of the iHelp system is user-driven based on the ergonomic principles considering pilot requirements and the system design/arrangement so that maximum interaction of users is achieved safely (Directive 93/42/ECC, 1993).

The deliverables within WP2 – “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp” and WP7 – “Impact Assessment” concerned with user requirements, personas, wireframing and validation collectively describe our usability process and form the “usability engineering file” stipulated by the requirements of the IEC 62366 compliance statement.

3.2 Process Implemented in iHelp

Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε. shows the steps performed to complete Task T2.4.

The following two inputs have been used to shape the initial version of wireframes:

- The characteristics of the target user groups based on their requirements from the system are specified using Personas in D2.8 – “User Centric Design I”.
- Use case models are developed based on the functional requirements in D2.1 – “State of the art and requirements analysis I”. to describe the sequence of actions between system components and the respective users.

The initial version of the wireframes was shared with the pilots in October 2021 (M10), and the feedback obtained during this workshop was used to create the second version of the wireframes. This second version was then demonstrated again to pilot users during user feedback workshops which took place in March 2022 (M14). The feedback obtained during this second iteration has been used to shape the final version of the wireframes presented in this deliverable, and to underpin two other main outputs of T2.4 – “User Centred Design”: UIX Design Guidelines considering the Context of using the system; and the usability KPIs which will be used to conduct a usability evaluation of the system in T7.2 – “Usability Evaluations of the iHelp Solutions”.

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L:2017:117:FULL&from=DE>

Figure 1: Flowchart for the activities in D2.8 and D2.9.

3.3 Summary Contents of D2.8

The contents of D2.8 formed an important milestone in developing the final outputs of this task and contained the final version of the persona's specification produced by T2.4 – “User Centred Design”. Its main components are summarised below, together with indications about any changes between D2.8 – “User Centric Design I” and D2.9 – “User Centric Design II”.

3.3.1 User-Facing Use Case Models

The functional requirements of different categories of users were investigated in T2.1 – “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp” and reported in D2.1 – “State of the art and requirements analysis I”. Main use cases are defined in which a persona's interactions with the system are encapsulated into well-described use case models to focus on the development of user-friendly UI.

Figure 2: Use case model of overall iHelp interaction with its Users.

A use case model, based on the most general pilot – the one of the Medical University Plovdiv is shown in Figure 2. It is designed to show a general overview of the interaction between the users and the iHelp system in a UI setup focused on three of the user types/personas: a Model Builder (Ken), Health Professional (Jill) and Individuals/Patients (Ann, Jack and Pat). The names used are labels of specific personas, identified and presented in D2.8. The interactions between the system and the fourth user type (Policy Maker) are explained in Section 3.3.5. Different interfaces are designed for each of the key user types. The annotations above each use case oval show which of the pilots this use case applies to using the abbreviations from Table 1.

Table 1: Abbreviations Indicating Relevance of Use Cases for Pilots

Abbreviation	Short Name of Pilot Lead	Pilot Lead
M	UNIMAN	The University of Manchester
P	MUP	Medical University Plovdiv
T	TMU	Taipei Medical University
G	FPG	Agostino Gemelli University Policlinic
S	HDM	Hospital de Dénia-MarinaSalud

Each use case and its interaction are explained in detail in the following sections.

3.3.2 Model Builder’s Interface

The persona Ken who is a health researcher or professional with advanced understanding of statistical modelling will be working on developing new models for risk prediction and customisation of the existing ones to accommodate local conditions within the “Developing Risk Prediction Model” use case. The

developed model will be embedded in the “Risk Assessment” use case of health professional Jill. Personal and educational requirements of the Persona Ken are obtained and are used in developing model builder UI. The interfaces are developed making sure they match the representations in the epidemiology domain and are concise/productive for the users.

3.3.3 Health Professional’s Interface

The health professional’s interface is used to assess the risk for a specific patient and advice how patients can reduce the chances of developing pancreatic cancer. Jill, being a doctor, has no technical knowledge about the system but is only interested in the well-being of the patients. She is trained on the already in-place Patient Information Systems which use a single screen with tables and charts. The interfaces are designed so that a color-blind health professional can use them. Moreover, if the system access request is made by a medical nurse with less authority, it should provide limited access to her. The following use cases are developed to provide this functionality:

3.3.3.1 Risk Assessment and Related Use Cases

The Risk Assessment is the initial use case triggered by an individual requesting the risk analysis by visiting a doctor’s office or a website. The standard flow of information between the Health Professional and the system is provided in Appendix A. Here the risk assessment model is run against the data available in the system and provided by the patient. If an elevated risk is detected, the use case is extended by the Elevated_Risk_Detected use case, where the system signals and explains the risk to the Health Professional and suggests further tests to be done using the Request_Tests_and_Samples use case.

3.3.3.2 Risk Mitigation Planning and Related Use Cases

The major use case for the health professional interface is the Risk_Mitigation_Planning. Clinicians work in collaboration with an AI model builder to provide a treatment plan based on the test results received from “Ingest_Tests_and_Samples_results” use case. The patient is profiled using a mobile interface when the risk of developing pancreatic cancer is high. The mitigation plan is proposed by the system and presented to a health professional to approve or amend according to the patient’s data.

3.3.3.3 Advice Review Use Case

The system responsible for delivering the risk mitigation plan to the patient will be generating a set of messages, some of which will require approval by the health professional involved in the risk mitigation planning of the specific patient. The messages requiring approval will be queued for the health professional’s attention and this will be prompted at an appropriate time. The interface for providing the approval will list messages and allow approval or modification of each message by the health professional.

3.3.3.4 Advice Follow-up Use Case

The mobile interface continuously monitors patients’ health data such as heart rate, and consumption of alcohol or cigarettes. When these health parameters are changed beyond specific thresholds, or when a pre-set period of time has passed, then the Advice Follow-up use case is triggered. At this stage, the advised mitigation plan is discussed with the patient and a new plan is sent to the advice delivery functionality of the mobile interface. The interface for this discussion shadows the interface enabling the initial risk mitigation planning with a very few differences.

3.3.4 Individual's Interface

The iHelp system is customised to be used by different groups of users. The interface design for the individual mobile interface and the display of messages is based on the different needs of the users to accommodate varied needs. Customers are differentiated using personas, the following three types of personas are considered in this project:

- Ann, who is a 40-year-old gamer, would not prefer to have some physical activities and is interested in achieving the results with less mobility.
- Jack, who is a 50-year-old professional can use apps with minimum guidance and is interested to work on his health parameters. He is diabetic and has a high risk of developing pancreatic cancer.
- Pat, who is 60 years old and is nearing her retirement, has been diagnosed with pancreatic cancer (early stage) and has poor eyesight and agility.

To cater to the needs of these groups of users, the following three uses cases are presented for the mobile interface.

3.3.4.1 Capture of Profiling Characteristics Use Case

The profiling questionnaire is developed in a dialogue-based form for the user and it is different for each pilot. Secondary data will be provided to the AI model for proposing Risk_Mitigation_Planning which is customised according to the user profile performed in this use case.

3.3.4.2 Risk Mitigation Delivery Use Case

The risk mitigation plan is delivered according to the individual profile with a customized message in this use case. There are various ways in which this plan can be sent e.g., list of actions that need to be performed or some goals being set or can be a coaching dialogue.

3.3.4.3 Risk Monitoring Use Case

The Risk_Monitoring uses the following two types of data:

- Biometric data from smart sensors or wearable devices regarding step count, pulse count, oxygen level
- Textual information regarding feelings, stress level and physical activity they have done.

When these values cross the expected threshold, Advice_Review use case is triggered from the Health Professional's interface.

3.3.5 Policy Maker's Interface

The consortium partner ICE is involved in the development of Social Media Analysis (T5.4 Social Analytics for the Study of Societal Factors and Policy Making), which is focused on analyzing the conversation of the public on various social media platforms on different topics. The data gathered from the analysis will be used by policymakers to have insight into current societal trends, and how the public perceives specific policies and their impact on the targeted communities. The outcome of the social analysis tool will be visualized through a user-friendly UI in the form of charts and graphs to show the trends of social interaction on different topics. Artificial Intelligence (AI), Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Sentiment Network Analysis (SNA) techniques are used in social media analysis for the identification of events and raising an alert based on the situations.

With this functionality, the main aim of the iHelp will be achieved to monitor the effectiveness of health-related policies, and outcomes from iHelp software.

Figure 3 shows the use case model for the social media analyser. The following subsections will describe the functional units of the social media analyser.

Figure 3: Social Media Analyser use case model – the perspective of Policy Maker user type.

3.3.5.1 Custom Social Media Analysis Solution

A set of docker containers which consist of different sub-components, i.e., NLP and SNA are created in the custom solution. Data is collected through Apache Kafka which is used for organizing data from various social media platforms and is communicated through dockers. Each of these dockers takes input from the social media source and provides output to Kafka. After this, the data is passed to other containers that are responsible for SNA and NLP before sending data to Complex Event Processing (CEP) containers. A dedicated data analysis rule is used in each CEP container for processing data on specific topics. It is the functionality of CEP to create alerts when certain rules are triggered. Alerts are displayed to the users on the GUI developed by Apache Superset.

3.3.5.2 Application Creation Use Case

Social media analysis “application” can be created by the users on the iHelp GUI webpage and each of these applications can be customized to monitor specific keywords or topics. GUI is available to the policymakers to create applications based on some rules and specify when to raise an alert when a certain threshold is reached. Applications can be viewed, modified, started and stopped from the iHelp GUI as shown in Figure 3.

3.3.5.3 Management of Alerts

The policymakers can review the alerts through the Alert List displayed on GUI and can also view the details of each individual using the Alert Information use case shown in Figure 3. Rules to trigger an alert are specified in the application when it matches some keywords or topics provided by the social media analysis tool.

3.4 Feedback on Key Screen Designs Oct 2021

The initial version of wireframes was presented to the potential end users for early feedback to ensure key screen designs are easy to use and user-friendly. The following are three groups of user pilots:

- Pre-clinical Pilots – Medical University Plovdiv (MUP) and the University of Manchester (UNIMAN).
- Pre-diagnosis Pilots – the Taipei Medical University (TMU) and Hospital de Dénia-MarinaSalud (HDM).
- Post-diagnosis Pilot – Agostino Gemelli University Policlinic (FPG)

The first round of feedback workshops took place in October 2021. The technical authors of the wireframes under the four main categories described in Sections 3.3, 3.4, 3.5 and 3.6 presented them to the pilots. A set of formative feedback questions were requested to be completed by the pilots to make interfaces in alignment with their expectations.

As a result of this feedback, the wireframes were updated and presented to the users once again in a second round of user feedback workshops in March 2022. This feedback is presented in the next Section 4.

4 User Feedback Obtained on Updated Wireframes

The user interfaces are divided into the following three categories:

- Clinician-Facing (DS4 and KODAR)
- Individual-Facing (iSPRINT and UniMan)
- Model-Builder and Policy-maker (UPM and ICE)

Each category held a separate workshop with representatives of all pilot users, ensuring all pilots had the opportunity to provide feedback.

Each responsible partner presented their wireframe stories to get feedback from the pilots before implementing the user interfaces in the actual system. The next subsection details the summary and suggestions from the workshops that are agreed on the way forward for developing iHelp for the needs of the pilot groups. Section 5.1 describes the suggestions for clinicians facing wireframes during the workshop. Feedback obtained on user-facing wireframes is discussed in Section 5.2. Finally, a demonstration of model builder and social media analysis is given in Section 5.3. Section 5.4 summarizes the main points, limitations and changes that will go forward into the other work packages.

4.1 Clinicians Facing Wireframes Workshop

The clinicians-facing wireframes design proposed by DS4 was presented in the workshop that took place on the 10th of March 2022. The workshop was attended by both technical partners (UPRC, UPM, ICE, ENG, SIE) and pilot users (HDM, TMU). A feedback form was created to get feedback from pilot users on the wireframes. All the interfaces were discussed; the recommendations from the partners on each screen are as follows:

- **Screen Risk Assessment**

During the treatment process, the change in the Body Mass Index (BMI) and weight should be visible to the healthcare practitioner. The partners responsible for developing a risk prediction model should closely collaborate with end-users to understand the risks and incorporate them into the prediction model. The developed risk model will show the results to the clinicians and the “disagree with the conclusion” button should be in the system where clinicians can write the reasons for the disagreement. This data will be useful for the model builder to improve the accuracy and outline any missed factors. The medication record of the patient should be shown by the system for a specific customizable time period.

- **Screen Risk Mitigation**

It was agreed upon by all partners that the button ‘Retrieve Test Results’ will show all the tests and their respective dates. Different recommendation strategies were demonstrated to pilots where the strategies are shown on a compact table or visual screen showing the consumption of alcohol with bottles and glasses of wine and beer. Pilots' recommendations are as follows:

- They would like to view the different options for the prevention plan.
- A visual presentation of the prevention plan should be printed and given to the patients.
- Clinicians should have the option to add mitigation actions from their side to the already provided prevention plan.
- **Screen “Advice Follow up”**

Pilots suggested during the workshop to record data on the correlation between risk factors and the development of cancer. This data would be useful for identifying risk factors that have more effect on developing cancer. This can be done at the back-end so it does not impact the user interface.

- **Screen “Advice Review”**

This screen should be presented as it is with no changes.

4.2 User Facing Wireframes Workshop

User-facing wireframes design proposed by iSPRINT were presented in the workshop that took place on 11th March 2022. The workshop was attended by both technical partners (UPRC, UPM, ICE, ENG, SIE, UNIMAN, FPG) and pilot users (FPG, HDM, TMU).

The interfaces built for iHelp on top of the mobile platform “Healthentia” were presented. The possibility of showing the information on a bigger screen e.g. tablet or laptop was discussed. iSPRINT clarified that the initial design has been made for the mobile application and the suggestion of scaling up to include tablets can be added as a development to the current design, yet it is not certain when this can be implemented, perhaps during any post-project exploitation stage.

4.2.1 Healthentia Application Demonstration

The use of the Healthentia application was demonstrated through the designed wireframes. Step-by-step interfaces are explained as follows:

1. Once the user downloads the Healthentia app, they can register themselves via the invitation code. With this step, the user will be registered in the iHelp database.
2. The screen with username and password can be made pilot specific reflecting various consent clauses.
3. Then there’s a screen with questionnaires to be answered, notifications and activities.
4. There can be a notification from the virtual coach that the coach wants to talk to the user.

4.2.2 Suggestions and Concerns

The suggestions given by the pilots about gamification, virtual coaching and the shape of the user interface are discussed. Moreover, privacy concerns and the developmental work that might need to be incorporated are outlined in this subsection.

1. Coaching needs to be fun to keep users engaged. Few designs should be developed and evaluated based on the user’s feedback.
2. There could be a delay in getting the patient’s data because this is not a common disease and they have a limited number of patients. The focus should be on the monitoring component while the virtual coaching would be developed at a slower pace.
3. The doctor should be able to write a message to be sent to the patient.
4. It has been agreed that the general shape of the user interface and the conversational paradigm of the content is very pilot-specific and therefore the conversation about the content would take place in WP5 – “AI for Early Risk Assessment and Personalized Recommendations” (customization of the needs of the individual users) and WP6 – “iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies” (customization of the needs of the pilots). It was noted that the Healthentia platform can provide the needed functionality.

5. One of the purposes of this meeting was to fix any potential differences between the flow of tasks and activities represented in T2.1 – “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp” and T2.3 – “Functional and Non-Functional Specifications”. A bit more work needs to be done to ensure consistency. The feedback sheets should be received from the pilots and probably they need to answer the question of whether the suggestion of a conversational paradigm is appropriate for their pilot.
6. The conversational interface should be more engaging. Gamification can be facilitated and a workshop can be arranged to discuss what can be done within the resource constraints of the project, e.g. showing some comparison graph or a quiz in a conversational style, or calculating what percentage each user has done towards their final goal.
7. A full leader board might not be feasible from a privacy point of view but individuals can be ranked by saying “you are 5th out of 20”.
8. This meeting was helpful from the WP2 – “Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp” point of view – the flows and the main architecture of the information. The content and personalization can be delegated to the Work Packages 5 and 6, ensuring content is aligned to specific needs of pilots and patient types.

4.3 Policy and Model Builders Wireframes Workshop

Policy and model builders wireframes design proposed by ICE and UPM respectively were presented in the workshop that took place on 14th March 2022. The workshop was attended by both technical partners (UPRC, UPM, ICE, ENG, SIE, KI) and pilot users (HDM, TMU).

4.3.1 Demonstration of Creating a Dashboard

UPM demonstrated the creation of a dashboard and showed the level of risk for a selected patient. Currently, the Decision Support System (DSS) using mockup data as the real-time data is not available yet. Some generic dashboards will be implemented and later on, customized dashboards can be added based on the pilot’s requirements. The customization of clinician’s view based on pilots requirements is aligned with the development of new risk models by the model builders type of users, and should be treated within the same risk management and software quality framework as the development of a new risk model.

During the demonstration, the HDM pilot was very impressed by the possibility of developing customized dashboards. This functionality is not usually provided by the other tools they use, yet the iHelp partners’ agreement was that any such feature should be only implemented within a full alignment with quality assurance practices of individual pilots related to new model development, and should be fully compliant with the constraints of developing medical software highlighted earlier in this deliverable.

4.3.2 Social Media Analysis Interface

The Social Media Analysis Interface was presented by ICE. The main aim of this interface is to capture and analyze data from social media platforms (Twitter, Facebook and Reddit) to help policymakers to improve policies. All data exposed by social media APIs is in the public domain so there will not be any breach of privacy.

4.4 Conclusion

The pilot workshops were useful to provide a collaboration platform for both the pilots and technical partners. The aim was for this collaboration to align perspectives on iHelp and enhance its functionalities,

making them more aligned to the needs of the pilots. Some additional features are to be added to the clinician-facing interfaces e.g., updating the risk assessment screen to show the change in BMI or weight during the treatment process. The prevention plan should be presented in different ways and then it is left to the clinician to decide which one would be preferred for a specific patient. The data about risk factors and the development of cancer should be recorded to understand the correlation between these two. All the messages sent to the patients should be authorized by the clinicians. To make coaching interactive in the Healthentia application, a few designs should be produced and select the best-rated one for implementation based on the user's feedback. The limitation for this would be obtaining sufficient user feedback in a representative set of contexts as this disease is not common and has a very limited number of patients in the clinical stage. In the later parts of that stage also the patients are seriously ill and they might not be interested to use coaching. Gamification and leader board are not part of the current Healthentia architecture and risk assessment components might be able to do it. This can be discussed between partners and can be delegated to other work packages. A new use case activity diagram can be made for the addition of a customized dashboard in the model builder interface if endorsed by all the pilots involved in the project.

5 Final user interface blueprints for generic iHelp system

The initial interfaces were reported in D2.8 – “User Centric Design I”, and used within a series of workshops to get feedback from the pilots and update the wireframes accordingly for the second round of interactions with pilot users. The results of this second round of interactions are reported in Section 4. Balsamiq Cloud³ platform has been used to sketch the consecutive versions of the wireframes and incorporate the improvements suggested in the workshops. Section 5.1 summarizes the model builder’s interface, 5.2 shows the changes performed on the health professionals' interface, and the individual’s interface updated designs are described in Section 5.3. Finally, Section 5.4 reports the wireframes of the Policy maker’s interface.

5.1 Model Builder’s Interface

The Model Builder persona is a data scientist in charge of training new or available AI Models, selecting the ones that best fit the pilot, and developing customized dashboards that can be shared with Health Care Professionals. To achieve this the DSS provides a set of functionalities like a workflow editor, execution of analytic algorithms and queries and visualization tools.

The Model Builder users will access the Model Builder interface where a set of components can be accessed: the workflow editor based on Node-Red⁴, the custom dashboards based on Node-Red dashboards and the AI Model explainability interface among others. Figure 4 shows the menu of the Model Builder user interfaces that gives access to the different components previously listed.

Figure 4: Model Builder UI menu.

Figure 5 shows the workflow editor interface. From this interface, the Model Builder user can create and store their workflows and dashboards using the drag-and-drop interface provided by Node-Red. The workflow interface is divided into different panels: the Nodes Panel, the Workflow Panel, the Node Configuration Panel and the Data Preview Panel. The Nodes Panel provides all nodes implemented under the iHelp project to interact with the Big Data Platform and the Analytic Workbench components. Those nodes allow to access the data stored in the iHelp Big Data Platform (iHelp Storage nodes palette) and to

³ <https://balsamiq.com/>

⁴ <https://nodered.org/>

select an AI-Model and invoke the execution of the model in the Analytic Workbench components (iHelp AI Models palette). There is a set of nodes available in the Node-Red framework that allows the creation of custom dashboards (dashboard nodes palette). The Workflow Panel allows the creation of workflows by dragging and dropping the nodes and connecting them, thus creating DAGs (Direct Acyclic Graphs). By clicking on the nodes added to the workflow editor panel, the Node Configuration Panel is opened. The Node Configuration Panel allows to configure each of the nodes. For instance, the Select iHelp Storage nodes allow the Model Builder user to configure the connection to the iHelp Storage, select the desired table, select the desired columns and filter the fields. Finally, the Data Preview Panel allows the Model Builder to preview the results produced by the query designed in the Workflow Panel. By selecting the different nodes implemented under the iHelp project, the Data Preview Panel displays the result obtained by executing the node, allowing the Model builder preview the data stored in the iHelp Big Data Platform or the result of the Artificial Intelligence Model configured in the Workflow Editor panel to be visualized.

Figure 5: Model Builder UI.

The Custom dashboards interface shows the dashboards created by the Model Builder in the Workflow Editor interface. Custom dashboards allow showing the data from the iHelp Big Data Platform and the AI-Models result using different types of charts like bar charts, pie charts and tables. Figure 6 shows a custom dashboard example. These custom dashboards can be accessed from the Health Care Professional interface.

Figure 6: Custom dashboard example.

Lastly, the Model Explainability interface will allow the Model Builder to interpret the results provided by the AI Models, check how the model result changes by modifying the values of the different model parameters and decide if the model can be trusted or has to be trained further. This interface is created based on Explainable Dashboard Python Library⁵. Finally, Figure 7 shows an example of the Model Explainability interface.

⁵ <https://explainerdashboard.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Figure 7: Model Explainability Interface.

5.2 Health Professional’s Interface

Persona Jill is a health professional, she uses the risk management interface to see all the available information when the AI system assesses the risk of the patient developing pancreatic cancer, and to give a correct advice to the individual. Advice is given by the health professional (also referred to as Clinician) which has observed the output of the AI subsystem of iHelp, displayed on the same screen where information about the patient and the case is shown. Since the health professional interface consists of confidential data, it is necessary to ensure security according to the standards at the medical institution. Figure 8 shows the screen which is password protected and has dual-factor authentication.

Figure 8

Figure 8: Login screen for the health professional - Password-protected access ensures confidentiality of data.

Figure 9 shows the Health Professional’s dashboard after the authentication screen. It has buttons for the four main use cases i.e. Risk Assessment, Risk Mitigation, Advice Review, and Advice Follow-up.

Figure 9: Health professional's dashboard.

5.2.1 Risk Assessment Group of Use Cases

The first step of using the iHelp system is to retrieve the details of the individual stored in the Holistic Health Record (HHR) shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Initial Screen detail of Risk Assessment Use Case.

The HHR record can be incomplete, or certain data should be updated during the visit, this is prompted by the health professional as illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 11: The system prompts for missing HHR data and additional information.

Once the missing details are completed, the “Calculate Risk” button is enabled, and the risk assessment model within the AI system produces an estimate of the risk for the individual to develop pancreatic cancer as shown in Figure 12. The system also provides additional explanations comparing the risk of the individual to the average risk for their peer group.

Figure 12: Displaying the calculated lifetime risk of developing pancreatic cancer.

The specific individual is predicted to have a somewhat elevated lifetime risk of developing pancreatic cancer, and the Health Professional is invited to confirm the conclusion or to disagree with it.

If they disagree with the prediction by the model, they are invited to record their considerations so that the AI model can be improved by the Model Builder Ken. The prompt is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: The clinician disagrees with the conclusion.

If the clinician agrees with the conclusion, the rest of the interaction between them and the iHelp system is described within the “Elevated Risk Detected” and the closely related “Request Tests and Samples” use cases. Within these use cases, the system offers some initial “what-if” suggestions as to how different factors can change the risk, and recommends some tests for the individual to do before the elevated risk of pancreatic cancer (or toxicity risk in one of the pilots) can be fully confirmed.

These options conclude this group of use cases, with the totality of information exchanged between the health professional and the system shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Conclusion of the initial risk assessment group of use cases when the elevated predicted risk is confirmed by the health professional.

5.2.2 Risk Mitigation Use Case

The second episode of interacting between the health professional and the individual occurs once the lab tests are ready. The health professional and the individual then would meet again to decide on the best course of action which can reduce the risk of developing pancreatic cancer or developing toxicity in the FGM pilot. This discussion is supported by the AI part of the iHelp system in the manner described below.

The initial steps are very similar to the risk assessment use case, with the patient data retrieved from the health record, and the information presented on the screen so that the health professional can fully consider it whilst interacting with the system and the patient. This stage of the dialogue is shown in Figure 15.

In the second stage, the test data is retrieved from the hospital information system. A modification of the system should be supported where the test data is entered manually by the health professional when some tests come on paper. The results of this second stage are shown in Figure 16. It is shown that this part of the system also allows the health professionals to explore different factors which contribute to the risk assessment. These factors are provided by the AI part of the system.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL https://ihelp-project.com/risk_reduction. The page title is "A Web Page". The breadcrumb navigation is "Home > Patient > Consultancy Session > Devise Risk Reduction Strategy". The left sidebar contains a tree view with categories: Patient Observation (Patient Details, Diagnoses, Medication, HHR Data, Family History), Risk Reduction (Test Results, Major Factors, Recommendation), Referral Files, and Known Allergies.

The main content area is titled "Patient Details" and contains the following information:

John Anonymous 29.02.71 51

Male 98 181 cm 28 -1.5 / 1 month

Date	Diagnosis	Notes	Follow-up
1/2/12	Flu	Not vaccinated	None
3/4/15	Acute Appendicitis	Referred	Operated
8/9/19	Health Check	All Clear	None

Medication	Type	Start Date	End Date	Dose
Candesartan	ARB	1/1/20	-	16mg/day

HHR Risk-related Data

Activity Level: Diet: < 3 servings of vegetables p/d

Sedentary Alcohol Units p/w

Walker Cigarettes p/d

Active

SportsPerson

At least one first degree relative is affected by pancreatic cancer

Patient diagnosed with chronic pancreatitis

Patient diagnosed with Type 2 diabetes or a problem with high blood sugar

Buttons: Psychological Profiling, Retrieve Test Results, Advise Risk Reduction

Figure 15: Retrieving patient details during the risk mitigation meeting.

Finally, to prepare the system for the next phase of recommending measures with which the individual can reduce the risk of developing pancreatic cancer or toxicity during treatment, this part of the system allows psychological profiling of the individual. This psychological profiling will help the system to personalise the messaging used for interacting with this individual. It does not need to take place during this second consultation visit, yet there could be situations where supervised input is necessary. The button for this psychological profiling is visible in the top right corner of Figure 16.

Once the button “Advise Risk Reduction” is pressed, the AI model in the iHelp system would calculate which measures are likely to reduce the likelihood of the individual developing pancreatic cancer, and will provide a concise summary list of these measures at the bottom of the screen as shown in Figure 17: The AI model in iHelp produces a shortlist of measures which can help reduce the risk for this specific patient. This is an invitation for the health professional to select some items in the list and this way to focus the remainder of the discussion with the patient supported by interacting with the system.

Once the selections are submitted, the system will display the detailed screen shown in Figure 18. It shows how the health practitioner can customise the advice to levels appropriate for the specific individual by parametrising the goals. On both this screen and on the previous one the health professionals can add an additional action/goal to the treatment plan. This additional action is limited to a set of actions which are agreed with the pilot-specific monitoring parameters so that the achievement of the action can be monitored by the software developed in Task 5.5 (Monitoring, Alerting, Feedback and Evaluation Mechanisms).

Another version of this screen is shown in Figure 19, providing an example focused on reducing both weight and alcohol consumption.

A Web Page
 https://ihelp-project.com/risk_reduction

Home > Patient > Consultancy Session > Devise Risk Reduction Strategy

Patient Observation
 ▶ Patient Details
 ▶ Diagnoses
 ▶ Medication
 ▶ HHR Data
 ▶ Family History
 Risk Reduction
 ▶ Test Results
 ▶ Major Factors
 ▶ Recommendation
 Referral Files
 Known Allergies

Patient Details

John Anonymous 29.02.71 51

Male 98 181 cm 28 -1.5 / 1 month

Psychological Profiling **Retrieve Test Results**

Date	Diagnosis	Notes	Follow-up
1/2/12	Flu	Not vaccinated	None
3/4/15	Acute Appendicitis	Referred	Operated
8/9/19	Health Check	All Clear	None

Type of Test	Result	Outcome	
Amylase	6	+	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Lipase	4	-	<input type="checkbox"/>
Epigenomic Age	62	!	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Medication	Type	Start Date	End Date	Dose
Candesartan	ARB	1/1/20	-	16mg/day

HHR Risk-related Data

Activity Level: Sedentary Walker Active SportsPerson

Diet: < 3 servings of vegetables p/d

Alcohol Units p/w

Cigarettes p/d

At least one first degree relative is affected by pancreatic cancer
 Patient diagnosed with chronic pancreatitis
 Patient diagnosed with Type 2 diabetes or a problem with high blood sugar

Major Factors Impacting Risk

Select Factors

Advise Risk Reduction

Figure 16: The screens for “test results retrieved” and “factors impacting risk”.

A Web Page
 https://ihelp-project.com/risk_reduction

Home > Patient > Consultancy Session > Devise Risk Reduction Strategy

Patient Observation
 ▶ Patient Details
 ▶ Diagnoses
 ▶ Medication
 ▶ HHR Data
 ▶ Family History
 Risk Reduction
 ▶ Test Results
 ▶ Major Factors
 ▶ Recommendation
 Referral Files
 Known Allergies

Patient Details

John Anonymous 29.02.71 51

Male 98 181 cm 28 -15 / 1 month

Date	Diagnosis	Notes	Follow-up
1/2/12	Flu	Not vaccinated	None
3/4/15	Acute Appendicitis	Referred	Operated
8/9/19	Health Check	All Clear	None

Type of Test	Result	Outcome
Amilase	6	+
Lipase	4	-
Epigenomic Age	62	!

Medication	Type	Start Date	End Date	Dose
Candesartan	ARB	1/1/20	-	16mg/day

HHR Risk-related Data

Activity Level:
 Diet: < 3 servings of vegetables p/d
 Alcohol Units p/w:
 Cigarettes p/d:

At least one first degree relative is affected by pancreatic cancer
 Patient diagnosed with chronic pancreatitis
 Patient diagnosed with Type 2 diabetes or a problem with high blood sugar

Major Factors Impacting Risk

Recommended Strategies

Factor^	Importance rank (1 - highest)	Strategy	Effort 1-10	Duration (months)	Target Value
Weight	2	Diet	3	4	BMI=20
Fat in Food	3	Reduce Fat	2	2	LDL < 110mg/dL
Smoking	1	Quit	10	2	1 cigarette/week
Sedentary Lifestyle	4	Exercise	7	6	5k / week

Figure 17: The AI model in iHelp produces a shortlist of measures which can help reduce the risk for this specific patient.

Figure 18: Detailed planning of risk reduction.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://ihelp.com>. The page title is "A Web Page". The breadcrumb navigation is "Home > Patient > Consultancy Session > Devise Risk Reduction Strategy". The left sidebar contains a menu with categories: Patient Observation (Patient Details, Diagnoses, Medication, HHR Data, Family History), Risk Reduction (Test Results, Major Factors, Recommendation), Referral Files, and Known Allergies.

The main content area displays a "Prevention Plan" with the following text:

You can lower your pancreatic risk by for example increase your exercise and healthy diet

Prevention Plan

4. Your weight now is kg
 In three months time, you will lose kg
 At the end of 6 months, your weight will be kg

5. Currently you drink Units of alcohol per week. The allowance is 14 units per week

ALCOHOL UNITS GUIDE

Pint of premium beer (5%) = 2.8 units	Pint of cider (5%) = 2.8 units	Alcopop 275ml (4%) = 1.4 units	Can of beer 330ml (4%) = 1.7 units
Gin / Vodka / Rum 35ml (37.5%) = 1.3 units	Spirits 1 litre (37.5%) = 37 units	Small bottle of wine 187.5ml (12%) = 2.3 units	Bottle of wine 750ml (12%) = 9.2 units

In three months time, you will reduce your alcohol consumption to units per week
 At the end of 6 months, you will have units of alcohol per week

Figure 19: An example of a risk mitigation plan focused on reducing weight and alcohol consumption.

5.2.3 Advice Review Use Case

The next use case, Advice Review, captures the interactions between the health professional and “their” part of the iHelp system, where they review the advice which the AI-part of the iHelp system has generated to send to a specific patient. This interface is shown in Figure 20. The health professional can use the interface to approve, modify or reject each advise message in turn. This is needed when messages generated by the system may impact the health of the patient in a significant manner. Establishing this is pilot-specific and the pilot-specific rules will be embedded in the system to flag a subset of all messages for review through this interface.

5.2.4 Advice Follow-Up Use Case

The last use case shown in Figure 21 is the Advice Follow-Up use case, where the Health Professional will meet the individual and review the progress against the objectives set, using the information gathered by the mobile interface and by the patient themselves. The meeting can also be called if the monitoring interface detects significant deviation from the objectives set. At the meeting the health professional will retrieve the details of the patient and any strategies set beforehand and will review the progress against any strategy. If a shortfall is detected, or a more detailed re-planning is necessary, they will click on the “Redress Shortfall” button and work with the screen shown in Figure 22.

Figure 20. Interface for Reviewing AI-generated messages from the system to the patient.

Figure 21. The “advice follow-up” screen.

Figure 22: Redress shortfall within the Advice Follow-up use case.

5.3 Individual's Interface

Previously released deliverables detailed that there are three separate advised delivery mechanisms that will be used in iHelp for individual interactions in the Healthentia mobile app (e.g., D2.1: State of the Art and Requirements Analysis I, and D5.6: Delivery Mechanisms for Personalised Healthcare and Real-Time Feedback I), namely: (1) data visualisation, (2) feedback messages and nudges, and (3) conversational coaching. The deliverable preceding this one, which reported on the first part of T2.4, provided a set of mock-ups for the individual interactions (D2.8: User-Centric Design II). As the conversational coaching mechanism was the most significant addition to the Healthentia application, these mock-ups mainly focused on this third delivery mechanism. In this subsection, we provide a summary of those mock-ups. As aspects of the Virtual Coach have been implemented, we also provide a short update on their implementation.

The mock-ups showed the Home screen of the Healthentia app (Figure 23, screen on the left), which featured two ways to reach the Virtual Coach. One was through a widget with a Virtual Coach message at the top of the Home screen. The other was through the Virtual Coach icon at the bottom right of the Home screen. Both interactions would lead to the Virtual Coach user interface which is shown in Figure 23, screen on the right. The first time the user visits the Virtual Coach they will see a short welcoming message, which they can close.

Figure 23: Screen numbers 1 and 2 of the Virtual Coaching UI wireframe.

After the user has closed the welcome message and on subsequent visits, interactions in this screen will look like the left mock-up in Figure 24 below, with the right image showing the screen after a reply has been selected by the user.

Figure 24: Screen numbers 3 and 4 of the Virtual Coaching UI wireframe.

With statements by the agent and reply-options that the user can select as the main interaction paradigm, the other following wireframes that were included in D2.8 then highlighted several elements within this type of interactions. The first element was the ‘thinking’ indication that was included to make the interaction with the coach appear more natural – as opposed to an instantaneous response by the coach. This aspect has been implemented, but instead of showing a ‘thinking’ bubble as was included in the mock-ups, there just is a small delay between speech-bubbles.

A second element that was shown in the mock-ups in D2.8 was a scroll bar for when the number of reply options would be high. This concept has not been implemented, but instead, a dialogue authoring strategy has been adopted to split a high number of reply options over two dialogue steps. For example, by adding the first half of the options to step 1 and then having an option ‘I have another question about this’ (or similar phrasing) to go to step 2, which would contain the other half of the options (and an option to switch back to step 1). This option was chosen because it feels more natural to ask for other options than to have a long list. Also, as indicated in the previous deliverable (D2.8) “in practice, dialogues should ideally be limited in the number of things a user can say in order to keep up the speed of the conversation”.

A third element that was shown in the mock-ups is the “What would your suggestion be?” response option that would lead the coach to make a suggestion for a topic to discuss. Design for the software components required for the agent making such suggestions is currently ongoing, and more elaboration on a possible approach for this can be found in D5.6.

A fourth and final element included in the mock-ups was the ‘continue’ button with a timer that could be pressed when there was another statement of the coach. This element has been merged with the implementation of the ‘thinking’ concept in a sense that the ‘continue’ button itself is no longer included, but there is a delay before the next dialogue step is shown.

The final mock-up in the previous deliverable (D2.8) showed an overview of what a longer interaction could look like (as shown in the left mock-up screen in Figure 25). The right screenshot in Figure 25 shows an interaction in the Virtual Coach interface as it has currently been implemented.

Figure 25: A mock-up screen showing a longer part of a conversation (left) and an actual conversation with the implemented Virtual Coach in the Healthentia app (right).

5.4 Policy Maker's Interface

ICE developed the Social Media Analyser in T5.4 (Social Analytics for the Study of Societal Factors and Policy Making) to provide an assistance tool for the policy maker to make informed decisions based of the information gathered and analysed from multiple social media platforms. The user interface screens for this tool are explained in the following sections.

5.4.1 Login Screen

The user logs in to the first screen using a secure authentication through an assigned username and password, as shown in Figure 26. The functionality is explained below.

Figure 26: The Login screen for the Social Media Analyser Tool.

After logging in to the system, the user is taken to the Applications List screen as explained in the Section 5.4.2.

5.4.2 Applications List

The Applications List screen is designed to provide an overall status of the tool as shown in Figure 27. It gives an overview of the whole system with the existing applications and the overall alerts generated by the applications running in the system. A widget is placed to show the total number of alerts generated by the application and number of active applications. Furthermore, a breakdown of alerts generated per application is provided for better insight.

Another widget translates the information of generated alerts into meaningful information shown in charts for users' understanding. A bar chart shows the alerts generated by applications. A heat map registers and explains the frequency of posts done from different regions. A line chart explains the number of posts done over the time.

The functionality is envisioned to make it convenient for the users to navigate through the activities, access existing applications, fine tune the application, change the status of an application or create a new one. The overview enables the user to understand the overall planned activity regarding the topics of interest and monitoring.

The following wireframe describes the envisioned functionality of the Application List UI.

Figure 27: Wireframe showing the list of existing applications within the Social Media Analyser Tool.

1. Grid showing the existing applications with ID, Name, Description and Status
2. Function to define/edit the rules of a particular application
3. Action button functionality to start/stop the application
4. Total alerts generated by the applications
5. Number of active applications
6. Breakdown of alerts generated by each active application
7. Overview of functionality available in the screen
8. Bar chart to represent the alerts generated by applications
9. A heatmap to identify the location of alerts
10. Line chart to show the frequency of alerts generated over time
11. Action button to create a new application
12. Action button to log out from the system

The Application list screen allows the user to navigate to the Application Details interface or the Create Application interface which are described in the sections 5.4.2 and 5.4.3 respectively.

5.4.3 Application Details

The Application Details screen interface provides the detailed information of a specific application in the system. As shown in Figure 28, the user is able to perform certain actions on a selected application. Furthermore, the screen shows the primary details as well as the list of keywords uploaded, which are used as trigger for alerts generation. A widget shows an overall count of alerts generated by this application with a function to navigate to the Alerts Information screen (section 5.4.5).

User can add or remove individual keywords to the lists shown in the interface and can also review the conditions and rules defined in the application.

Figure 28: Wireframe showing the details of a specific application within the Social Media Analyser Tool. Further functionality buttons allow the user Create a new application (section 5.4.4) or go back to the Application list (section 5.4.2).

1. The detailed functionality available in this interface is described below:
2. Primary details of the application
3. 1st List of keywords uploaded in the application
4. 2nd List of keywords uploaded in the application
5. Conditions and Rules defined in the application to generate alerts
6. Functionality to add/remove specific and individual keywords in the existing lists
7. Number of alerts generated by this application
8. Action button to navigate to Alerts Information screen (Section 5.4.5)
9. Action button to navigate to Applications List screen (Section 5.4.2)

5.4.4 Create Application

The Create Application interface allows user to create and define a brand-new application with specific focus and topic of interest as shown in Figure 29. The first section in the screen allows the user to define the basic details like ID, Name and Description of the application. In the next section, the user will select the desired social media platform, select the desired language of the posts and select the category (applicable to Reddit). User can upload up to two separate keywords list files (CSV format) in the next section. Once uploaded, the keywords are summarized in the list of keywords.

After defining the basic application, the system allows the user to fine tune the application functionality by providing the functionality to construct a nested condition instance, that would assist in capturing the data according to the specific keywords uploaded in the application.

It can further be narrowed down by defining rules by limiting the frequency of specific keywords within the context of a specific topic of interest. This functionality allows the user to capture data from the social

media streams and avoids generating unnecessary alerts data that may prove to be detrimental in drawing meaningful conclusions.

The wireframe in Figure 29 describes envisioned features of the Create Application screen.

Figure 29: Wireframe showing the Create Application screen.

The annotations on the wireframe are described below:

1. Define the ID, name and description of the application
2. Select the social media platform, language, and category (if applicable)
3. Functionality to upload keywords list file in CSV (Excel) format
4. List of uploaded keywords in the system
5. Define conditions based on the keywords uploaded and functionality to create a nested condition instance
6. Add new condition to limit the scope of alerts generation
7. Define rules to fine tune the application for capturing data within a specific context or topic of interest
8. Complete the creation of application and submit to start

After the user is able to register/create a new application on this screen, the user should be able to return to the Applications List Screen, where the newly created application should be visible – as explained in Section 5.4.2.

5.4.5 Alerts Information

Once the designed applications are performing the real-time analysis of social media data, they are expected to generate alerts when the defined rules are triggered. The following wireframe is designed to describe the information concerning alerts that will be generated by running applications.

As shown in Figure 30, the user should be able to see the alerts generated by all running applications. In addition to the simple sub-section (showing a list of alerts with relevant information), the wireframe also illustrates several visualisations that are designed to provide a quick overview of the alerts' related information.

The first part of the screen shows a detailed overview of the last two alerts generated by this application with the time of generation, the text of the post, polarity, subjectivity, sentiment, and the trigger word. It also allows the user to identify potential influencers within the scope of this application and follow the individual on the specific social media platform.

The next part of this screen contains meaningful data visualised in different charts and graphs. This information will be derived in view of the recommendations made by the clinicians and policymakers.

Figure 30: Wireframe showing the screen where detailed conditions and rules of each application can be defined.

1. Detailed information of the alert generated based on the conditions and rules defined. The widget includes information about the user and the post. Furthermore, it represents the different attributes for this alert
2. Follow the user identified as a potential influencer
3. Pie chart to show meaningful information based on the discussions with policy maker
4. A bar chart information to visualize data
5. A line chart information visualization

Once a user completes defining the rules and conditions for an application, they can return to the main Application List screen (Section 5.4.2).

5.4.6 Follow Users

Based on the discussions with the policymakers and clinicians during the GA meetings, workshops, and research, it is realised that the social media analyser tool would not only extract some crucial data that may assist in the policy making process but could also be instrumental in disseminating effective information by identifying users as influencers. Hence the functionality in section 5.4.5 is developed and the results are displayed in this section. The screen in Figure 31 outlines the general information about the users identified as influencers and followed. A pie chart information displays the contribution of each influencer within the scope of this application and topic of interest.

The table on the screen lists down the exact text from the posts which generated the alerts in the application. The system user can select the relevant influencer from the list to view the posts directly from the social media platform.

Figure 31: Wireframe showing the main alerts screen where alerts of all active applications are shown.

The annotations shown in the above wireframe (Figure 31) are described below:

1. User can view the list of all influencers (assigned with an ID number) in this table matrix
2. A pie chart information showing the contribution of each influencer within the context of this application
3. List of the posts made by the selected influencer

6 User Interface Design Guidelines

As a result of the work accomplished in T2.4 – “User Centred Design”, we have derived a number of user interface guidelines for the look-and-feel of the iHelp user interfaces. These guidelines are then reflected in the usability evaluation KPIs which are described in the next section.

D2.8 – “User Centric Design I” stipulated that we need a focus on the following aspects of the iHelp user interface:

- Personalisation – especially the content of the messaging in the mobile interface;
- Interactivity – user actions on the interface should have an immediate and transparent effect;
- Arousing and retaining attention – following the Fogg Behavioural Model (Fog., 2019);
- User-centric design process – users and pilots remain involved in the development.

Section 6.1 describes the general principles of UI design, followed by a template of desktop interface detailed in section 6.2 and a mobile interface given in section 6.3 to reflect the UI design principles.

6.1 General Principles of UI Design

General principles of UI design depend on the system requirements, e.g., if security is an issue, it is better to provide limited access to the user instead of making interfaces password protected. The following are three main categories of usability principles (D., F., A. + 04):

1. Learnability: how easy it is for the target users to learn the new system;
2. Flexibility: how flexible is the new system in accommodating different users and tasks;
3. Robustness: how transparent is the system operation for its target users?

The sequel of this section explains each of the subsections in turn, using material from a number of sources including (D., F., A. + 04; Thim., 90):

6.1.1 Learnability

Learnability is when the system makes it easy for the new user to have an effective interaction and when it also achieves the maximal level of performance. Some of the principles that support learnability are as follows:

- Predictability: Predictability is when the user’s history of interaction is sufficient to determine the outcome of his future interaction with the interactive system.
- Synthesizability: The user can estimate the result of the previous operation on the current state.
- Familiarity: New users of the systems bring with them knowledge of a wide range of existing application domains. Familiarity is the measure of the existing knowledge of the user to achieve effective interaction. The interfaces should be designed using the conventions typical for the specific operating system and mode of interaction, for example, desktop interfaces under Windows or MacOS should have a “File” menu at the top left corner, and mobile interfaces under Android should provide access to the extended menu under the “hamburger” icon.
- Generalizability and consistency: The interactive system should work the same way as already in the existing systems. The generalized layout must be followed so that the user’s learning on the previous system can be carried over to the current system which minimizes the stress on the user and in turn reduces the error probability.

6.1.2 Flexibility

Flexibility describes the ways in which an interactive system and the end-user exchange information. The following principles define the flexibility of the interaction:

- **Dialogue initiative:** When the interaction between user and system happens, it must be taken into consideration which partner has the initiative in the conversation. When the system initiates all dialogues meaning that the user only responds to the requests is called dialogue system pre-emptive. Alternatively, when the user has the freedom to initiate the action towards the system, it is called user pre-emptive. The interactive system should be more user pre-emptive and less system pre-emptive which will allow the users to have maximum flexibility.
- **Adaptability:** The system should be able to provide specialized interfaces for visually impaired users and less dextrous users. In contemporary operating systems these adaptations often happen at the level of the operating system, but the designers should check how their interfaces look when these adaptations are applied.
- **Task migratability:** A good principle for the interactive system is to allow the user to interrupt the system at any time and resume the interrupted activity at the user's request.
- **Customizability:** The interactive system should have the property to be modified by the user or the system. The order of the tasks cannot be anticipated as the user may perform the same task in different ways. Therefore, the system should not have a fixed order to complete a task.

6.1.3 Robustness

The robustness of the interactive system is determined by the features that help to achieve and assess the system goals successfully.

- **Observability:** Observability is the ability of the user to assess the system from its clear description. Based on "WYSIWYG (what you see is what you get)", the user interface should have an accurate presentation of the task in the form of a picture representing something real. These can also be mapped to the concept of "affordances" – the user interface should provide prompts standing in for tasks which can be initiated.
- **Recoverability:** Users can make mistakes in initial interactions; therefore, the system should provide an option of recovery when the error is recognized.
- **Responsiveness:** It is the duration of time needed by the system for a response to the user. Instantaneous response time is required for interactive systems.
- **Task conformance:** Redundant coding and checkpoint are used for task conformance. When a user provides input to the system, it should ask for data compatibility e.g., date format. A checkpoint is needed to confirm from the user if he wishes to proceed with irreversible actions and the frequent user response may become automatic.

In the following sections, we will see how these principles are reflected in draft interface designs split between desktop interfaces and mobile interface screens. These prototype screens are different from the wireframes presented earlier. Whilst the wireframes are designed to show the functions and contents of the desktop interface, the prototype screens below demonstrate the key design elements and colours which will comprise the different system interfaces, without indicating functionality to be covered. The colours used on these screens are exemplified through approximate rendering in Annex A - Recommended Colour Chart.

6.2 Desktop Interface

The desktop interface is targeting clinicians and policy makers. They will be working on high-resolution monitors in indoor environments which are not too bright and can follow the standard desktop metaphors and layout to ensure meeting the familiarity and predictability principles.

Looking at the layouts shown in Figure 32 and Figure 33, we can discern the following elements:

- A vertical menu bar on the left-hand side of the panel which presents the main functions pertinent to the specific interface set and the patients registered with a specific clinician is shown. The clinician can see the progress of each patient in a separate panel.
- The identity of the professional logged into the system is displayed as their photo. Usually, this is in the top right corner but here we propose to keep it in the more prominent position of the top left corner because of its importance for accessing the right patient details and ensuring transparency of who is operating the system in the case of users having forgotten to log out, etc.
- Figure 33 shows the multi-panel of the patients

Figure 32: Example layout and colours for the health professional desktop interface – a main panel version.

Figure 33: Example layout and colours for the health professional desktop interface - multiple panels version.

6.3 Mobile Interfaces

The mobile interface consists of two categories – auxiliary pages and functional pages. The previously proposed designs for these interfaces distinguished auxiliary pages (the landing screen and the thinking screen) and functional pages (home screen with widgets, info screens for different pages) as shown in Figure 34 and Figure 35. The auxiliary pages were proposed to have a neutral color scheme to keep them aligned with the desktop interface, and the functional pages were aimed to have richer colors to intrigue the user to use the application interface as shown in Figure 34.

The design of the custom iHelp template for the functional pages within the Healthentia mobile app has been further developed and is now implemented (as also reported in D5.6 – “Delivery mechanisms for personalised healthcare and real-time feedback I”). Screenshots showing an impression can be found in Figure 36.

Figure 34: Proposed landing page on mobile interface (left) and processing (thinking) page (right).

Figure 35: Example colour scheme for the mobile interface - Progress to Goals screen (left) and Daily Status screen (right).

Figure 36: The iHelp theme as implemented within the Healthentia application.

7 Usability Evaluation KPIs

7.1 General Evaluation Principles

The evaluation of the user interface of iHelp will take place within WP7 – “Impact Assessment”, based on the KPIs explained in this section. The evaluation will be organized in two stages (S., H., 04):

- **Formative evaluation by usability experts:** This is performed early on in the time period of T7.2 – “Usability Evaluations of the iHelp Solutions” and is designed to guide developers by providing them with timely and useful feedback regarding any problems users are likely to encounter when using the system. Also, there is some evidence that experts are more effective than user testing in identifying problems with usability at this stage of development (M., Is., 18).
- **Summative evaluation by actual end users:** This will take place closer to the end of the project, and will see clinicians, policymakers and end users go through specific scenarios of using the system, and provide scores based on their impressions.

In the next two sections below, we expand on each of these two phases in turn.

7.2 Formative evaluation by usability experts

The cognitive walkthrough method (P., L., R., + 92) is used for usability inspection meaning that the user’s knowledge and understanding of the tasks are acquired through experience, thought and the senses. This is a type of heuristic evaluation conducted by experts, who observe some usability heuristic rules (N., M., 90).

Within the cognitive walkthrough method, a task list is generated, and analysis is then performed on its goals and subtasks. It is then followed by experts performing a “walkthrough” and asking a set of questions to determine the usability. Usually, the following four questions are asked (P., L., R., + 92):

- **Will the user try to achieve the effect that the subtask has?** E.g., the user should know that a subtask is performed to achieve this specific user’s target.
- **Will the user notice that the correct action is available?** E.g., is there a tab or button?
- **Will the user understand that the wanted subtask can be achieved by the action?** E.g., an option is given to the user, but the user is unable to understand its action and therefore will not click on it.
- **Does the user get appropriate feedback?** Is the user getting appropriate feedback so that they know that the right action is performed?

Several recommendations are provided for each subtask to reduce the possibility of the error. Priority is given to every recommendation to make sure the maximum usability of the system.

7.3 User-based usability testing – Summative evaluation

A set of workshops with different user groups will be organised in collaboration with each pilot. Representative users will be asked to undertake specific scenarios under the observation of a usability specialist, and any mistakes will be discussed to find out the deficiencies in the user interface causing these and feed these into the final round of improvements.

Once the task is completed, the target users will be asked to score the system on the following criteria by completing a short questionnaire based on 5-point Likert scales:

- Usefulness of the system: How useful do users find the system?
- Effectiveness for achieving goals: How effective is the system for achieving the work goals of the health professionals and the health-related personal goals of the users?
- Ease of learning: How easy was it to learn the system from scratch?
- Ease of use: How easy was it to use the system and to obtain help regarding its use?
- Any discrepancy between the scores given under these criteria and the observations of the users performing sets of tasks will be discussed with the users to identify the reasons between the overall opinion and specific actions or mistakes, thus validating the summary validation measures.

In addition, we will also measure use continuance – the rate with which the system is used near the end of the trial period compared to the rate with which the system is used near the start of the trial period. The rate of use will be collected through system logs on an anonymous basis.

8 Summary and Conclusion

8.1 Summary of the Deliverable

The second stage of the overall process of T2.4 – “User Centred Design” is reported in this deliverable. This second half of T2.4 – “User Centred Design” has focused on incorporating feedback from different user groups i.e., clinicians, patients, model builders, and decision-makers in the updated wireframes. We also provide user interface guidelines for the technology developers to ensure iHelp software will be in alignment with the requirements of end-users.

This deliverable:

- Reports the user-driven process and its results given in D2.8 – “User Centric Design I”;
- Provides final user interface layout for the iHelp software;
- Describes the summary of the feedback obtained from the pilots on the first version of wireframes and how these changes will be implemented;
- Details the general principles for UI design;
- Outlines the KPIs for usability evaluation.

This deliverable provides baseline guidelines for the developers to make iHelp software effective and enjoyable for end-users ensuring long-term use. The KPIs defined in Section 7 will be used to evaluate the effectiveness of the iHelp system later on.

8.2 Further work

General principles of user interface design and KPIs defined in this deliverable will be part of the evaluation work near the end of the project, undertaken under T7.2 – “Usability Evaluations of the iHelp Solutions” in WP7 – “Impact Assessment”. We will continue to work in line with the developers to ensure the UI design guidelines are incorporated into the iHelp system. Usability evaluation of user-friendly interfaces produced for the iHelp software will be evaluated based on the KPIs described in this deliverable.

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List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Applications Programming Interface
BMI	Body Mass Index
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEP	Complex Event Processing
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
DSS	Decision Support System
ENG	Engineering Ingegneria Informatica SpA
EU	European Union
FPG	Agostino Gemelli University Policlinic
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HCI	Human-Computer Interface
HDM	Hospital de Dénia-MarinaSalud
ICE	Information Catalyst for Enterprise
iSPRINT	Innovation Sprint
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MUP	Medical University Plovdiv
NLP	Natural Language Processing
O	Objective
PM	Policy Maker
PC	Pancreatic Cancer
SotA	State of the Art
SNA	Sentiment Network Analysis
T	Task
TMU	Taipei Medical University
UC	Use Cases
UCD	User-Centred Development
UI	User Interface
UNIMAN	University of Manchester
UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
UPRC	University of Piraeus Research Centre
UX and UIX	User (interface) eXperience (design)
WP	Work Package

Annex A - Recommended Colour Chart

Table 2: Recommended Colour Chart

Colour	Specification (in HEX)	Use
	#04B499	Lighter colour at bottom of landing and login pages, side bars, etc.
	#094C5F	Darker colour as top of landing and login pages, side bars, etc.
	#00FFC4	Active buttons and iHelp logo.
	#4C9D9D	Input fields on mobile and desktop pages.
	#F51E49	Attention-signalling parameters and chart elements, possibly with negative connotations
	#00D170	Important but positive parameters and chart elements, often with positive connotations
	#FDD2DA	Background shade of softer red (negative), can also be used to denote weekends in diary charts
	#DEFFF7	Background shade of softer pastel cyan – positive information can also be used for workdays in diary charts.